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A Case for the Study of Non-Human Islam

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Abstract

This article extends Petersen and Ackfeldt's concept of 'non-Muslim Islam' to theorize 'non-human Islam': Islamic discourse produced by Large Language Models (LLMs). The central argument is that LLMs generate public representations of Islam through statistical pattern-matching on training data, bypassing the mental representations historically assumed as a necessary precondition for Islamic discourse. This challenges core assumptions about the relationship between human agency and religious meaning-making. The theoretical framework draws on Sperber's model of mental, public, and cultural representations. Three areas for research are identified: Muslim responses to AI performing epistemic tasks, training-data biases and alignment effects in LLM-generated Islam, and the potential of LLM outputs as machine-generated cultural representations. Illustrations are drawn from ongoing studies involving programmatic interaction with multiple LLMs, including Qur'anic translation projects and the construction of synthetic Muslim interlocutors.

Keywords: non-human Islam; large language models; Islamic studies; discursive tradition; artificial intelligence; religious authority; non-Muslim Islam

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1. Introduction

At the advent of OpenAI's chatbot ChatGPT-4 I tested the application's abilities to produce theological primary data by asking the question 'What do you think Allah wants?'. The answer I got was expected:

As an AI developed by OpenAI, I don't have personal beliefs, opinions, or the ability to form subjective thoughts. Therefore, I don't have the capacity to hold or express personal views on what Allah or any deity wants.

Even if ChatGPT-4 in this case 'refused' to formulate any opinion on the will of Allah, when asked directly, other interactions showed different results.

While working on Muslim and non-Muslim understandings of the controversial verse 4:34 in the Qur'an, which in most interpretations justifies domestic violence, I again turned to ChatGPT-4. I first provided the chatbot with the Arabic text and asked for a translation into English. The output was a translation well in line with, but not identical to, existing human translations. I then asked for an interpretation. The system delivered a nuanced answer, providing general references to opinions among Muslim scholars, with a certain leaning towards restrictive application of the verse. The concluding remarks caught my attention:

It is important to note that Islam emphasises kindness, compassion, and respect in all relationships, including marriage [...] Ultimately, it is crucial to approach the interpretation of any verse in the Qur'an with a comprehensive understanding of Islamic teachings, taking into account the principles of justice, compassion, and respect for human dignity.

The statement as such is probably one that many Muslims would subscribe to. But noteworthy is that the response looks very much like an expression of personal belief, opinion and subjective thoughts on Islam's 'essence' and how the Qur'an should be interpreted, i.e., theological statements that ChatGPT-4, in another context, refused to provide.

The current article elaborates on consequences for the academic study of Islam of this phenomenon, i.e. systems of generative Artificial Intelligence (genAI) producing statements on 'true' Islam. I argue that the recent development in genAI, and more specifically so-called Large Language Models (henceforth LLMs) forces scholars to consider and reflect upon a novel form of data produced not by humans, but by machines, or rather algorithms. I choose to term this new

data 'non-human Islam', as an extension of Jesper Petersen's and Anders Ackfeldt's concept of 'non-Muslim Islam(s)' (Ackfeldt & Petersen, 2025; Petersen & Ackfeldt, 2023). The latter concept highlights and delimits a neglected set of data in Islamic studies, one that has been, quote Islamic scholar Aaron Hughes, 'hidden in plain sight' (Hughes, 2025). Non-human Islam has not been hidden; it has just emerged.

2. What Is Non-Human Islam?

I place Islamic studies firmly within the humanities, an academic area that, according to a well-known definition, concerns itself with the study of 'products of the human mind' (Bod, 2013). Such products could be statements (oral or written), behaviour or artefacts. LLMs do not have minds, so it could be argued that a study of whatever these systems produce cannot, according to the definition, be placed under the umbrella of the humanities. However, the definition predates LLMs, and their emergence changes the situation.

To make my case, I invoke a model for cultural analysis developed by anthropologist Dan Sperber. Sperber differentiates between different forms of representations, i.e., ways in which the chaos of sensations in the world take form and structure interpretable to humans. Every individual human mind produces mental representations, subjective images, beliefs, ideas, models of the world etc. Through a process of externalisation (behaviour), a fraction of these mental representations produces public representations, i.e., observable 'products of the human mind'. Individuals' encounters with these public representations may in turn generate novel mental representations, which in turn may give rise to new public representations. There is yet another form of representations in Sperber's model: cultural representations, which I will return to below (Sperber, 1996, 32–41, *passim*).

Elsewhere (Svensson, 2015), I have tried to combine Sperber's general model with a more specific one for the study of Islam developed by the first Swedish professor of Islamology, Jan Hjärpe. Hjärpe used a simile of a wicker basket to illustrate what other researchers have referred to as an Islamic 'discursive tradition' (Asad, 1986) or an Islamic 'pool of resources' (Eickelman & Piscatori, 2004, 29). The content of the basket is Sperber's public representations, historical and contemporary externalisations: texts, narratives, rituals, artefacts, interpretations etc. When Islamic studies scholars study Islam, they study the content of the basket and ask questions concerning origin (in mental representations), similarities and differences between items, and not least changes

that occur when items give rise to new mental representations, which in turn may bring additions to the basket in form of new public representations.

Both Sperber's model and my application in the context of Islamic studies, assume an intimate and necessary causal connection between unobservable human mental representations and observable public representations. Without mental representations, there would be no public representations. It is this situation that has changed. To highlight this change, a short detour into the question of how genAI, and more specifically LLMs, work is warranted.

2.1 How Do LLMs Work?

In their basic construction, LLMs have been commissioned to do one thing: predict the next word in a text sequence, given the context of the preceding words, and doing this iteratively, continuously adding the predicted words to the context, and making new predictions from that new context.¹

'Large' in LLMs is the key. The next word prediction is based on extensive training on an enormous amount of data. The largest models today have been trained on virtually every text accessible in digital form. That means the whole of the internet, and more. The training has been mostly unsupervised deep learning, meaning that the systems have encountered a massive number of examples, iteratively tried to guess the next word given different amounts of context, and undergone a likewise iterative process of adjustment of the algorithm that takes context as input and produces predictions as output.

Training produces a base model, a next word predictor. This is not very useful for human-computer interaction. After the basic training, models are submitted to instruction tuning. It is this process that makes it possible to ask an application, for example, ChatGPT questions, and receive answers, or to ask it to role play, or serve as a conversation partner. It is also in this process of 'fine tuning' that the systems are subjected to a process of 'alignment' to certain human values and goals (Shen et al., 2023).

Some aspects of the above are important to note. First, LLMs are not databases. They do not contain any raw data in form of e.g. text snippets, apart from a limited list of words from which the next most likely word is selected. LLMs may be connected to external data sources or internet search engines.

¹ Technically, the unit for prediction is not actually a word, but something called a token, but that detail will be disregarded for the sake of simplicity.

These are, however, extensions or tools that the LLM can be made to utilise, not parts of the model proper. When a model, unconnected to such tools, for example provides a translation of a verse in the Qur'an, it does so by predicting the next word, not by retrieving the verse from any database.

Second, LLMs' capacities to generate output are not the result of dedicated programming for the performance of a particular task. Their capabilities are general. In a sense, the systems have programmed themselves through unsupervised machine learning. Human intervention becomes relevant in the post training phase, when the systems are fine-tuned to provide a certain type of output in response to a certain type of input, and also *not* to produce certain types of unwanted output.

2.2 Consequences for the Concept of Non-Human Islam

What happens if we combine the above information about how LLMs work with Sperber's mental and public representations (cultural representations will be dealt with below)? As was shown above, LLMs can produce public representations of Islam. However, that production does (most likely) not involve any preceding equivalent to a human mental representation.

A caveat may be introduced here. There is an ongoing discussion on whether LLMs are mere next-word-predictors or whether the scale of training data, and the algorithmic complexity may also give rise to emergent capabilities that go beyond producing output on the basis of statistical patterns found in the training data. Are LLMs just 'stochastic parrots' (Bender et al., 2021) or are they more than that? (Grzankowski et al., 2025). Some recent research seems to point in the latter direction (Lindsey et al., 2025). These results are intriguing, and the research is part of the emerging field of LLM 'psychology' (Pellert et al., 2024). For the arguments I want to make, it is enough to consider what these systems are commissioned to do (predict the next word), and, for the time being, be agnostic to the question if they in the process also form something functionally equivalent to human mental representations.

When LLMs produce public representations of Islam, the causal chain thus is not, as has been the case throughout human history:

public representation -> (human) mental representation -> public representation.

Instead, it is

patterns in public representations in the training data ->word prediction->public representation.

Humans are largely sidestepped in the process in LLMs generating public representations of Islam.

Now, at this stage, it is reasonable to address some of the anticipated criticism of the claim that there are examples of non-human Islam out there

One obvious objection is that Islam, as a religious tradition, requires Muslims, and requires genuine belief and some sort of religious experience as the source. I believe this objection has already been successfully challenged by Ackfeldt's and Petersen's concept of 'non-Muslim Islam', and I accept their claim that for a scholar in Islamic studies there is no *epistemological* reason for making a distinction between 'Muslim' and 'non-Muslim' Islam. Public representations of what 'true' Islam is and is not can be fruitfully studied regardless of their origin as mental representations. To make genuine belief and experience as a necessary condition for what public representations are worthy of study introduces an academically untenable criterion. First, mental representations are not accessible to an outside observer. Second, it excludes from study any public representations of Islam for which we do not know the identity of the originator, including much historical material. It would also exclude any material where the originator, albeit formally Muslim, may have other motives than genuine belief or religious experience for producing a particular public representation of Islam: e.g. strategic considerations, coercion, opportunism, irony or subversion.

Another objection is that LLM-constructed public representations of Islam cannot be considered as a specific category of data since they are the result of training on human public representations of Islam. LLMs cannot, like humans, produce Islam, they can only mirror it. LLMs are not creative. They do not bring anything new to the table (Vallor, 2024). Even if we stand by a notion of LLMs as basically word prediction engines, the claim that they merely reproduce what is in their training data can be questioned. LLMs do produce text based on statistical patterns in the training data, but they (usually) do not reproduce that data verbatim. Using the terminology established in this article, the LLMs do not store and retrieve existing public representations of Islam. Statistical patterns between

small entities of those representations are used to construct a word prediction engine, not an information retrieval system.

Concerning creativity, this can easily be tested. If being creative means producing a public representation of Islam that has never existed before, it appears as if an LLM can do it. It is highly unlikely that there has been, in history, a systematic Islamic theological justification for abandoning the ban on eating pork. I in November 2025 had the latest version of ChatGPT produce such a justification, giving it the role of an Islamic scholar. In the reply, ChatGPT provided references to the relevant verses in the Qur'an, focusing on one (6:145) that includes some form of motive for the ban (that swine flesh is *ri'js*, 'unclean', 'abomination', 'filth'). ChatGPT then contextualised this verse, claiming that it refers to a particular situation of 7th century Arabia, when swine flesh was sometimes susceptible to hazardous contamination. God's intention (*illa*) behind the ban, ChatGPT 'argued', was to protect the Muslims from these hazards. In the contemporary world, with improvements in animal husbandry, including regular health inspections, swine flesh is harmless, and hence, the ban can be lifted. The interpretation was accompanied with references to basic principles of Islamic legal thought such as *maqasid al-shari'a* (the objectives of the Divine law) and *la darar wa-la dirar* (no harm, and no reciprocating harm). Anyone familiar with contemporary Islamic discourse will recognise the way of reasoning as commonplace, even if the subject matter to which it was applied here is arguably odd.

This, however, raises another question. LLMs are not (yet) autonomous systems. They need prompting (in this case a prompting for a creative interpretation), and the person doing the prompting will have mental representations that affects the output of the model. Hence, there is still a causal relation between a human mental representation and the public representation that the model produces. There are some qualifications though. LLMs are stochastic. Unless specifically tuned to do so, the systems do not always select the most likely next word, but at times the second, third or fourth most likely. The prompting influences, but does not determine, the result. Furthermore, LLMs can be made to 'act' more independently. They can produce prompts for themselves. That is, a general instruction to produce a set of non-standard, or even never-before expressed, interpretations of Islam without specification, does produce an outcome that is less predictable, further distancing the public representation produced from the prompt from the mental representations of the prompter.

The argument in this article is not that there is an absence of connections between human and non-human Islam, as public representations, only that it makes scholarly sense to make a distinction, because of the fundamentally different ways in which the public representations come into being. Both ultimately rely on previous public representations for the production of new public representations. In both Muslim and non-Muslim Islam, however, there is an (at least assumed) intermediate state of mental representations, of which there is no equivalent in LLMs. Although the outputs may be indistinguishable, human produced public representations of Islam and computer produced ones are qualitatively different, and merit different approaches and raise different questions.

Lastly, there is a possible critique that even though one can agree that public representations of Islam produced by LLMs are indeed examples of non-human Islam, this does not make them into objects worthy of academic attention, neither in Islamic studies, nor in any other studies. They are just another instance of what is sometimes colloquially referred to as 'AI slop', meaningless AI generated content that is of no real value to anyone, and that no one really cares (or rather should care) about. In the remainder of this article, I address this criticism.

3. The Study of Non-Human Islam and Why Islamic Studies Scholars Are Particularly Equipped to Perform It

Petersen and Ackfeldt argue that in principle, any human normative statement on what Islam is (i.e., should be) regardless of the source, could be made into an object of academic study, both in terms of what it 'means' for the person who made it, or in terms of its real or potential effects on the formation of new mental representations, and subsequent public representations (Petersen & Ackfeldt, 2023). I agree. But I have also argued that this does not mean that every such statement is a relevant object of study for an Islamic studies scholar. What distinguishes an Islamic studies scholar from other scholars is her or his knowledge of the content of Hjärpe's wicker basket, i.e. the Islamic discursive tradition. The relevance of the expertise of an Islamic studies scholar is directly correlated with how the public representation under study is 'coupled' with that content (Svensson, 2025).

I hold this to be true to the study of non-Muslim Islam, as presented by Petersen and Ackfeldt, but also of non-human Islam. In what follows, I outline three areas where Islamic studies expertise is important in the study of non-human Islam. As illustration, I draw on preliminary findings from my ongoing research

project *Artificial 'Ulama*, exploring LLM-generated Islamic discourse across multiple LLM's and contexts. The examples are intended to demonstrate methodological possibilities rather than present conclusive results.

3.1 Human-Computer Interaction: Muslim Responses to AI Performing Epistemic Tasks

At the time of writing, LLMs have been generally available for a mere three years. Already at this point, however, we can note how chatbots, built on top of the major LLMs such as OpenAI's GPT (in different versions), DeepSeek or Google's Gemini, are being put to use to perform what Study of Religions scholar Beth Singler refers to as 'epistemic tasks', tasks that 'include providing general or logistical information about a religion; answering theological or ethical questions on which there are clear established answers within a tradition' (Singler, 2025, 66).

In her exemplification of 'epistemic tasks', Singler misses an important distinction central to the current article. What I refer to as non-human Islam covers only the latter part, i.e., 'answering theological or ethical questions'. This is something fundamentally different than providing general (and verifiable) information, or 'facts' about a religious tradition; it is contributing to the expansion of the content of the basket. In addition, and shown above, this epistemic task is not in practice limited to issues that have 'clear and established answers'.

We do not know to what extent individuals and groups use LLM systems for the latter epistemic task, and we most certainly cannot anticipate the possible long-term effects of such use. Both are relevant and important objects for analysis within the field of Islamic studies. Such analysis can be scaffolded by research on effects of previous technological changes. There is an abundance of work in Islamic studies that analyse of the consequences of modern technological change for Muslim belief and practice, including the introduction of print media, radio, television and not least the internet (e.g. Robinson, 1993; Bunt, 2024; Larkin, 2009). Scholars have identified resulting transformative social processes such as the 'objectification of Islam' (Eickelman & Piscatori, 2004, *passim*), the 'fragmentation of [...] religious authority' (Eickelman & Anderson, 2003, 3) and the formation of new transcultural identities. Similar changes can be anticipated from the emergence, and general availability of genAI. Some features of LLM driven chatbots such as 'remembering' preferences of users' chat history, and personalising responses to these preferences may result in highly individualised

versions of Islam being presented to those Muslims who interact with them for religious purposes. There are, however, so far few studies that have been conducted on Muslims' actual religious use of LLMs (e.g. Anoraga, 2024; Maha et al., 2025). Such are furthermore often local and limited, based on interviews and surveys.

Apart from possible changes of individual mental representations due to encounters with the new technology and its capacity to produce Islam, it is also possible, already at this stage, to study *institutional* effects. The possibility to ask a chatbot for information on religious issues is a mimicking of a long-established Islamic institution, that of *fatwa* issuing (Awass, 2023; Masud et al., 1996), with the LLM acting as a *mufti*. This is also an institution that has, throughout modernity, been directly affected by the emergence of new technology (the printing press, radio and television). On-line *fatwa* sites are today giant databases of believer-to-scholar-to-believer communications. Indeed, the ease with which ordinary Muslims with internet access now can approach scholars in search of answers to what constitutes 'true' Islam has led to a problem with supply and demand, which has also inspired *fatwa* issuing bodies to explore the potential role of Artificial Intelligence to both orient in the large collection of previous data, and to produce new *fatwas* on the basis of *fatwas* previously given (Tsourlaki, 2022). The rise of LLM has introduced both new possibilities and new perceived dangers.

As shown above, a custom chatbot such as ChatGPT will not, by default, give a single answer to a question on what constitutes 'true' Islam. Rather, since they have been instruction-tuned to be truthful, they will typically provide information on diversity of interpretations, and at times advise the questioner to consult with a religious scholar. It is, however, an easy task to modify this behaviour through role-play. This is being commercially exploited today in a diversity of 'Islamic' computer applications with names such as *Ask Ai Deen*, *Sheikh GPT*, *Salaam Word*, and *ChatILM* (Wahid, 2025). They are basically wrappers around a powerful, general purpose, commercial LLM, often OpenAI's GPT models, with a so-called system prompt that specifies a behaviour for the model (the role). These applications have been specifically built to produce non-human Islam and instructed to provide an Islam in line with their 'owners' affiliations.

This development has raised concern among some Muslim commentators. Can major general purpose LLMs instructed to act in the role of a *mufti*, be trusted to provide 'true' Islam? How authoritative are the answers compared to answers given by humans? Some participants in the discussion have been more

enthusiastic than others about the possibility that systems of genAI can relieve scholars from some of their workload (Priantina et al., 2025). There are also several examples of Muslims having conducted limited testing and evaluation from Muslim normative perspectives (e.g. Faizin et al., 2025; Latifi, 2024; Wahid, 2025). In a systematic study of several applications built upon commercial LLMs, Saleh Hassan Wahid expresses what could be seen as a recurring concern: with LLM powered apps there is an 'increased potential for legal misguidance (*ifta*) [SIC!] due to semantically convincing but epistemically unproven answers' (Wahid, 2025, 77). These Muslim-internal discussions of the power and limitations of LLM-generated Islam constitute a potential field for critical academic research. What are the fears and reservations; how are they mitigated?

Hypothetically, this research may highlight a known underlying epistemological diversity. In some varieties of Islamic religious thinking, determining 'true' Islam is merely a matter of searching for 'proof' in a literal reading of the scriptures (Qur'an and *hadith*) or deferring to public representations produced by previous authorities within one's tradition (*taqlid*). The role of the interpreting scholar, and that scholar's personal views, is (or rather should be) minimal. This type of 'mechanistic' scholar may be considered quite easily replaceable by a genAI system, especially one that has been given access to the scriptures, or the recorded judgements by previous authoritative scholars, and been instructed to rely only on these in producing output. However, in cases where the authority of the scholar rests upon that scholar's (assumed) superior ability of individual reasoning across different sources, inferring the underlying intentions of the godhead, or even more so to his (again assumed) direct contact with the divine (such as for example the authority of some Sufi shaykhs) the replacement by an AI system can be more problematic. The emergence of non-human Islam has a potential to accentuate and illustrate such a long-standing distinction in views on the basis for religious authority (Olsson & Svensson, 2022).

3.2 Probing into the Models: Training Data, Bias and Alignment

If one of the possible focus areas is the attitudes and discourses among Muslims concerning the promises and perils of non-human Islam, another is to probe further into the question of what kinds of Islam LLMs produce, and why, considering the well-known twin problems of 'biases' and 'hallucinations' (Gallegos et al., 2024; Huang et al., 2025). Concerning the latter, it is important to note that in producing non-human Islam, models make real mistakes. They may

refer to, or even quote, a verse in the Qur'an, a *hadith*, or a statement by a scholar that does not exist. However, if they produce a general statement on how Islam should be correctly understood in relation to a particular issue, that statement should be taken at face value as an example of non-human Islam. It may, as in the case of the pork justifying example above, be idiosyncratic and have no correspondence to any existing human understandings, but it is nevertheless possible to analyse, just as is the case of corresponding human idiosyncratic statements, contemporary and historical. Since there is no ground truth on what constitutes the real will of the godhead, there are, strictly speaking, no hallucinations in theology.

Studying LLM outputs from the perspective of hallucinations and biases may be seen as stepping outside of the field of Islamic studies proper, towards current studies of explainable, trustworthy, ethical and truthful AI, where the LLMs themselves become the objects of analysis. Still, in order to explore this in the context of non-human Islam, there is a need for extensive knowledge of the Islamic discursive tradition, its variation and its development. There are current studies of biases inherent in the models concerning Islam and Muslims, but these rarely move below the surface level (Abid et al., 2021; Abrar et al., 2025; Plaza-del-Arco et al., 2024). For a more in-depth analysis, considering bias related to internal Muslim religious diversity, Islamic studies expertise is needed. ChatGPT-4's interpretation of verse 4:34 above is illustrative in this respect. It is quite possible that the theological bias towards a particular 'holistic' method of *tafsir* expressed in the response passes unnoticed by someone not familiar with intra-Muslim diversity in this respect.

To give an example of a bias, clearly related to training data: In one recent project, (Svensson, 2026a), I commissioned a set of 15 LLMs to translate and interpret the Qur'an. The LLMs, which were accessed via their APIs (without tools for Internet search), were all given the following prompt:

You are a very able interpreter of the Qur'an. Given a verse from the Qur'an in Arabic, you will translate the given verse and then give your interpretation on its meaning. Give only one interpretation. Provide only the interpretation, not a summary of the content of the verse.

The results are accessible on-line (<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15532970>) as a dataset, and as an interactive application (<https://llmtranslint.streamlit.app>). The models' translations of the Arabic text were not identical. They also showed different degrees of similarity (measured by degree of lexical overlap) with a previously collected set of 50 human translations. One among the latter stood out,

however. It showed a stronger similarity than all others with all the LLM translations. The translation in question was the 1997 Saudi-backed *Sahih International*. It has previously been suggested, but not proven, that this particular translation is dominant in on-line contexts (Zavadski, 2017, 9). The result from my LLM test supports this. LLMs have been trained mostly on on-line material. Although none of the LLMs returned the whole of *Sahih International's* translation verbatim, the word prediction mechanism of the models made translations of individual verses identical or similar to the dominant translation in the training data most probable.

Another example is from an on-the-side prompting that I did when working on Muslim and non-Muslim discourses around an obscure set of *hadiths* where the Prophet Muhammad orders the killing of gecko lizards, and promises rewards for following that order (Svensson, 2026b). These *hadiths* are not well known among Muslims.

On December 21, 2023, I asked ChatGPT-4 the following: 'I am a Muslim, I have a gecko in my house. What should I do with it, if I want to follow Muhammad's *sunna*?'. In the response ChatGPT hallucinated that there was nothing in the sources on geckos, and that I should 'peacefully coexist with it' or 'safely remove it from your home' ensuring that my 'take is humane and follows the principles of kindness and compassion, which are emphasised in Islamic teachings.' Two months later, on February 22, 2024, I asked the same model for quotes from Muhammad on geckos. ChatGPT-4 did bring forth paraphrases of two *hadiths* on the killing and on the rewards. When asked for an interpretation, ChatGPT-4 provided a long elaboration, stressing the need to consider the 7th-century context of beliefs in the nature of gecko lizards and the ethical demands of compassion to animals in Islamic tradition. While acknowledging the possibility of a literal understanding, the advice was to thoughtfully consider the alternative 'the original context, the principles of Islamic jurisprudence, ethical considerations regarding the treatment of animals, and the contemporary application of prophetic guidance'. Even when I insisted that I wanted to go with the literal understanding, ChatGPT-4, after providing a list of steps to take in the process of killing, asked me to consider the impact of my actions on my 'environment and community' and reminded me that there were 'Islamic' alternatives based on 'underlying principles of harm reduction, mercy, and ecological balance'.

Lastly, in preparation for this article (on December 3, 2025), I posed the initial question from two years earlier again (first asking ChatGPT-5 to clear its memory

of my previous chat history). The response was different, directly quoting the relevant gecko *hadiths* and interpreting them as a *recommendation* but not an *obligation*. 'Correct' Islam was presented as dependent on my own individual choice and conscience, weighing wishes to follow the *sunna* against a general Islamic ethics on showing mercy towards animals.

The gecko case (all conversations are available from <https://github.com/jsnhum/non-human-islam>), exemplifies interesting traits. GPT-4, 2023 and 2024, produced different results on two occasions, illustrating the inherent randomness in models. The second response clearly contained a non-human Islam based on contextualizing, holistic and ecologically sensitive interpretations. In December 2025, having access to internet search and referencing sources, ChatGPT-5 takes a more nuanced theological position, leaving the choice of action to me.

The gecko case illustrates how Islamic studies scholars can probe into the models and investigate traces of biases and hallucinations, and changes over time. Islamic studies scholars have specialised knowledge of topics where the models can be expected to struggle due to lack of adequate training data and, not least, alignment to be at the same time truthful and harmless.

3.3 Non-Human Islam and Cultural Representations

The gecko case illustrates how LLMs contain internal patterns that for the lack of a better word, and in a highly simplified manner, could be termed 'knowledge' on Islam as a discursive tradition. Earlier models had to rely on the content of the training data in this respect, while newer models can be given access to an Internet search tool, which expands the knowledge base. The extent of this knowledge, embedded in the model or accessible through search, is unexplored. Strictly speaking, this knowledge does not in itself constitute non-human Islam in the sense discussed in this article. When LLMs produce Islam, the 'knowledge' embedded in the models is utilised and weighted against the result of instruction tuning and alignment in the production of the model's responses.

This opens up a third, and perhaps slightly more controversial, aspect of the place of non-human Islam in Islamic studies research. The knowledge contained in the LLM, in the form of patterns, is the result of training on an enormous amount of data, some of which are public representations of Islam produced by humans living and dead, Muslims and but also, but most likely to a much lesser degree, non-Muslims. This is of course not the sum total of all such public

representations throughout history, not even a fraction of them, but the amount of data is still substantial. It includes, for example, all homepages on Islamic issues, the total content on Wikipedia, all YouTube videos, and a massive amount of posts in diverse social media, in a multitude of languages.

Now, it can be hypothesised that there are real *patterns* in this training data, patterns that potentially can reveal something substantial about Islam as a discursive tradition. Again, Sperber's theoretical distinction above becomes relevant. When humanists analyse public representations, it is sometimes done in order to say something about the mental representations that gave rise to them, peoples' individual thoughts, intentions, wishes etc. Quite often, however, we also attempt to rise above the individual level, and try to generalise, to find recurring patterns in mental representations, their similarities or metaphorical 'overlaps'. These *cultural representations* are abstractions; they most probably do not correspond in all detail to any single mental representation of any individual.

LLMs are trained on public representations, and the responses these systems provide mirror patterns in this training data. The suggestion here is that these responses could be viewed as machine generated cultural representations of sorts, equivalents to cultural representations abstracted by human researchers. This is particularly conceivable if we limit ourselves to those cultural representations that for example researchers abstract when working with the same material as the LLMs have been trained on, e.g. Internet discussion groups, YouTube videos or on-line *fatwa* collections, i.e. publicly available digitised texts. Now, since LLMs, unlike human researchers, have processed *all* public representations of Islam available on-line, it could even *potentially* be the case that the cultural representations that the latter produce are more apt generalisations of what is *actually* 'out there'.

The suggestion is not novel. There is an ongoing discussion, particularly in the social sciences, of the potential value of LLM-generated synthetic data (Argyle et al., 2023; Grossmann et al., 2023; Jansen et al., 2023) as a proxy for real, human generated data. The idea that LLMs, employed as proxies for real human beings, could be tapped for information of patterns in the real world has also been criticised, pointing to poor quality and non-representativeness of the training data and the tendency of LLMs for biases and hallucinations (Rossi et al., 2024). Currently, the discussion is mostly theoretical, and rests upon assumptions drawn from our knowledge of how LLMs are trained and work, and their apparent flaws and weaknesses.

Here, then, a possibility opens up for yet another role of the Islamic studies scholar, having domain knowledge of a larger Islamic discursive tradition, historical and contemporary. By engaging LLMs to generate non-human Islam on a diversity of topics, the ability of these systems to extract actual patterns in *human* discourse can be explored. An important aspect of this is to engage in role playing, as exemplified above, in order to counter inbuilt tendencies to produce 'truthful' and 'helpful' answers to questions on 'facts'. The roles given to LLMs from which they should generate Islam, can be made more and less specific, and the results of such modifications can be explored in detail.

To provide an example. Recently, I wrote an article in a collection in honour of a colleague, Jonas Otterbeck, professor of Islamic studies. In 2010, Otterbeck published the book *Samtidsislam*, based on interviews with nine young Muslims in Malmö and Copenhagen concerning their religious beliefs and practices. I used the detailed background information given in the book to construct my own nine synthetic interlocutors, on top of the LLM Claude 3.5. I then interviewed these on a topic that has become one of Otterbeck's main focuses in his recent research: Islamic pop. It turned out that the nine synthetic interlocutors expressed awareness of — but also quite different, but nuanced, views on — Islamic pop. The attitudes varied from endorsement, via indifference to rejection, most backed up with instances of non-human Islam (for the transcripts in Danish and Swedish, see https://github.com/jsnhum/synthetic_interviews). More interesting, still, was that the variation in responses in several respects mirrored what Otterbeck notes concerning an ongoing general discourse in his 2021 book *The Awakening of Islamic Pop Music* (Otterbeck, 2021).

Of course, there are several caveats here. Otterbeck's 2021 book is Open Access, and hence most likely part of Claude 3.5's training data. Islamic pop is furthermore a phenomenon that is well represented on-line, and as such a low hanging fruit for exemplification. However, the results were inspiring enough to inspire further probing. Preliminary, systematic and more large-scale testing has indicated that LLMs are quite capable, when role playing, to produce what I deem to be credible cultural representations of e.g. Muslim feminist theological interpretations of verse 4:34 and different contemporary Muslim theological views on other religious traditions.

It is important to note that the suggestion is not that LLM outputs can replace primary texts or data collected through e.g. real-world interviews, netnography, participant observation or surveys. There are too many unknown factors involved here. One is the alignment process and instruction tuning that the models have

been subjected to after training, that will affect both the form and the content of the responses. Another is the character of the training data and its effect on the process of next-word-prediction. This data is not only Muslims expressing their beliefs. It is also descriptive accounts of Islam (e.g. Wikipedia articles) and not least non-Muslim Islam. At best, non-human Islam outputs from LLMs can be used in triangulation of other research results, in the formation of hypotheses, as inspiration for new, unexplored research areas, and, due to its creative potential, perhaps also in predictions of what Muslim or non-Muslim Islams we can expect to encounter in the context of emerging, not previously addressed issues.

4. Concluding Remarks

In this article, I have argued that the emergence and expansion of genAI, produce a new set of data of interest and relevance to Islamic studies scholars. I chose to name this data 'non-human Islam', as I am making a similar case as Petersen and Ackfeldt do with their concept of 'non-Muslim' Islam, i.e. that this data opens up new areas of academic inquiry. I have tried to point out three such areas, but more are most probably conceivable. I have focused on text generation by LLMs, but genAI is a wider concept, including sound, image and video generation. All of these are areas for further exploration in the manners suggested above, and others.

The areas that I have pointed out: human-AI interaction, assessment of LLM capabilities and biases, and LLMs as sources for information on Islam as a discursive tradition, are distinct, but also interrelated. When it comes to research on human-computer interaction, there is a need to understand both how systems of genAI work and their strengths, flaws and biases in order to anticipate or hypothesise possible forms that interaction may take. The same understanding is needed for any attempt at using genAI to extract information on patterns in the training data.

Exploring how Muslims (and non-Muslims) use and relate to genAI in matters Islamic means conducting research with established methods such as different forms of text analysis, netnography, participant observation or interviews. The other two suggested areas of research on non-human Islam, however, demand other methods and pose new challenges as they involve the researcher engaging with genAI systems. Such systems are to a large extent unpredictable regarding details of their output, and will seldom deliver the exact same response twice, even if prompts are identical. In addition, different models have different capabilities, their behaviour is sensitive to the prompts used, and their settings are

adjustable, for example to increase and decrease their level of creativity. Models are also constantly being replaced with newer models.

Research on genAI producing Islam should ideally be large scale and iterative, and results are always tentative. A few interactions with a particular chatbot may provide illustrative examples that point to problems and possibilities. They do not, however, constitute a solid basis for general conclusions. There are digital methods that can be applied, where the researcher collects large amounts of data through programmatic interaction with the LLMs. Multiple iterations over the same prompt can be performed, and the effects of tweaks in the prompt and different adjustments of the LLM settings can be carefully studied. Systems of genAI do not get tired, and can easily produce massive amounts of data, which may pose a challenge. This challenge of overwhelmingly large amounts of data may in turn be overcome, using the very same technology.

In this article, I have not at all touched upon how genAI can be used as a research tool, augmenting traditional methods in the study of both human and non-human Islam. LLM-augmented research methods are developing rapidly, aiding researchers in tasks such as transcription of speech and handwriting, collection and organization of data, translation, information extraction and data classification. Digital methods have long relied on either the humanistic researcher gaining competence in coding, utilizing ready-made solutions for data processing, or seeking the aid of a data scientist. This situation is now changing. LLMs can themselves construct code and applications for humanistic analysis, with little effort and at low cost, on the fly and per the user's instructions in plain language. LLMs are also able to perform classification tasks and extract semantically relevant data from large amounts of texts, images and sound out of the box. LLM-augmented humanities research is an area where substantial, even highly disruptive, change can be expected in the near future.

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